

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON USING TEASER AND MESSAGE TECHNIQUES IN SASSO COCKS-SEMEN COLLECTION AND EVALUATION OF SEMEN QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

The reproductive capacity of poultry birds (cocks) is greatly influenced by the quality of their semen, and it is impossible to overestimate the significance of semen evaluation in poultry breeding for the selection of breeding males or continuous monitoring of their reproductive performance. Based on body weight, Sasso cocks may be worth considering in any breeding program. The massaging technique, however, could be challenging to perform when gathering semen due to its size. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the semen quality characteristics concerning the time and body weight of twelve (12) Sasso cocks that were reared intensively for twenty-four (24) weeks. Through examination of the semen and microscopical analysis of motility, sperm concentration, sperm morphology, body weight, life-to-dead ratio, active motility, pH, and glucose concentration, the features of the semen were evaluated. After two weeks of the experiment, the cocks were divided into three (3) groups, T1R1, T2R2, and T3R3, which correspond to treatments I, II, and III. Semen was then extracted utilizing the abdominal massage technique. Another set of 4 each of Sasso hens and local hens were used as teasers in T2 and T3, respectively. The study groups did not differ statistically ($P < 0.05$) except for semen volume, total semen count, and response time to semen collection. Because the Sasso cock breeds are readily available to farmers, they responded well to the use of teaser hens in semen collection, and the qualities of the spermatozoa and semen appeared to be unaffected, they are suggested for semen production to lower the costs of importing more exotic breeds for breeding programs. **Keywords:** Artificial Insemination, Poultry Species, Teaser, Massage and Spermatozoa Quality.

INTRODUCTION

Semen quality assessment in male poultry species is an important aspect in determining egg fertility and hatchability, which subsequently impacts hatchery business profitability. It serves as a reliable indicator of reproductive capability (Abdurrahman *et al.*, 2016, Wondmeneh and Adey, 2011). As noted by Tarif *et al.*

(2013), the quality of poultry semen encompasses spermatozoa concentration and motility, in addition to semen volume, pH, and glucose level. Ganpule (2018) asserts that the Sasso is the highest quality coloured broiler breeder developed solely from original parent breeding stocks in France. The statement indicates that it is resilient, manageable, and regarded as a

versatile bird, contributing to its extensive popularity. Owing to these attributes, the Sasso cock is a well-respected strain and could serve as an excellent research bird for breeding programs that showcase the application of artificial insemination. Unfortunately, the weight may not be suitable for the conventional massage method of semen collection due to the risk of injuries and discomfort during the massage for semen collection in large poultry species. This has often resulted in the continuous use of antibiotics and anti-stress medications, which may be detrimental. Consequently, utilizing teasers to gather semen from ruminants, pigs, and rabbits (Dominiek *et al.*, 2011; Barszcz *et al.*, 2012) could be a practical alternative to the standard massage technique employed in poultry. The quality characteristics of poultry birds' semen significantly impact fertility and the hatchability of eggs, which provide a reliable measure of their reproductive ability (Bilalissi *et al.*, 2022; Peters *et al.*, 2008). Conversely, hatchability and fertility are the key elements that dictate hatchery business profitability. The quality of a male's semen remains one of the most vital factors affecting his fertility.

One of the most significant subsectors of livestock is poultry, which provides an inexpensive source of high-quality animal protein in the form of meat and eggs. Livestock is a substantial subsector of agriculture (Tunsisa and Berihun, 2022). Given that the production of poultry presents significant prospects for creating jobs, enhancing family nutrition, empowering women, and guaranteeing food security in households (FAO, 2019), It is essential to characterize the quality parameters in terms of body weight, total count, sluggish motile, active sperm, live sperm, pH concentration, semen volume,

semen colour, and glucose concentration. The fertility of all poultry species gradually diminishes as the male's age advances due to changes in semen quality factors (Tunsisa and Berihun, 2022). The quality of the semen produced by poultry birds (cocks) has a substantial impact on their reproductive capacity (Abdurrahman *et al.*, 2016). Genetic factors have been discovered to influence hatchability and fertility across different breeds, variations, and individuals within breeds (Abdurrahman *et al.*, 2016). Umesiobi (2004) described several assays for evaluating semen quality, although these have rarely been implemented on farms. Historically, the industry relied on colour and volume characteristics to evaluate semen and determine sperm quality (Okereke *et al.*, 2008).

To evaluate male teasing and identify any genital tract disease or infection, semen volume and colour are also examined (Tarif *et al.*, 2013). Factors such as breed and strain, age, cock body weight, collection method, and diluents used can all influence semen quality (Mosenene, 2009). Some indications of breed and seasonal variations may also impact semen production in cocks (Tuncer, 2008). The collaborative strategy, as indicated by its name, necessitates collaboration from the donor birds and may employ external behavioural stimuli such as food, nesting materials, or vocalizations (Hamerstrom, 1970). Since there is no handling of the birds, the technique's benefit is that the birds remain neither stressed nor harmed. This approach has the principal advantage of yielding a substantial quantity of semen free from contaminants like urine and faeces. Nevertheless, the volume of the semen collected will be lower, which represents the disadvantage of this method. In the instance of Muscovy ducks, the

cooperative procedure approaches showed promising results using artificial vaginas (Gvanyahu *et al.*, 1984). In this context, it is especially important to emphasize the employment of dummy or teaser females (Rybnik *et al.*, 2007).

According to Gordon (2005), domestic cockerel semen has an average sperm concentration of 5000×10^6 sperm/ml. However, according to Hafez and Hafez's (2000) report, the average sperm concentration in semen taken from domestic cockerels is between $3000-7000 \times 10^6$ sperm/ml. According to Gordon (2005), the abdomen massage technique ejaculates an average of 0.25 ml. According to Bah *et al.* (2001), the average semen volume was 0.28 ± 0.14 millilitres. Nonetheless, it was shown that the recorded semen volume varied from 0.37 ± 0.02 to 0.73 ± 0.01 millilitres (Peters *et al.*, 2008).

It is crucial to understand that the total number of sperm collected per ejaculation will depend on the amount of semen and the concentration of sperm (volume multiplied by concentration). This information may help calculate the maximum number of insemination doses that can be made (Senger, 2003). Bird species and breeds have slightly varying semen pH values. The ideal pH range for semen is 7.0–7.4. In contrast to a pH of 6.4 (acidic), which is unsuitable for semen storage because it may harm the sperm cell's plasma membrane, sperm motility is typically high between 7.0 and 7.4 (slightly alkaline), which also improves fertilizing ability (Latif *et al.*, 2005).

On the other hand, several experiments conducted by Donoghue and Wishart (2000) suggest that chicken sperm can withstand a pH range of 6.0 to 8.0. Bah *et al.* (2001) reported a semen pH ranging from 7.54 ± 0.04 to 7.80 ± 0.03 ; Peters *et al.* (2008) likewise found the cockerel's semen

pH to be somewhat alkaline, with a mean of 7.01 ± 0.01 . Numerous causes could be responsible for this variance in semen pH. The pH of ejaculated semen, in particular, depends on many secretions. According to Salisbury *et al.* (1978), low-quality semen typically contains a lot of fluid from the accessory glands, which raises the pH of the semen. Since the semen collection tubes are narrow in design, sperm will likely break down the fructose in the semen to lactic acid under anaerobic conditions, lowering the pH of the semen as the time between collection and measurement rises. According to Salisbury *et al.* (1978), semen samples with a high concentration of dead sperm may transform into ammonia, which will raise the pH. The present study aimed to outline the methods of semen collection in roosters and to evaluate the characteristics of seminal fluid in roosters.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The experiment was carried out at the Department of Animal Science livestock farm unit, Faculty of Agriculture, Nasarawa State University, Shabu-Lafia campus, Nasarawa State. The study area lies between latitudes 7° and 9° Northland longitudes 7° and 10° East. Given its position, it experiences a tropical climate. According to the Faculty of Agriculture weather station (2022), the temperature ranges from 20°C in October to 36°C in March, with an annual rainfall of around 1168.90 mm. From a sizable population of Sasso birds raised in a deep litter system at the Teaching and Research Farm at the Shabu-Lafia Campus of Nasarawa State University in Following a random selection process, twelve 24-week-old cocks were weighed, housed separately, and given two weeks to acclimate. Ad libitum access to cool, clean drinking water and breeders' mash was provided. Each of the twelve Sasso cocks was given four to the Control group (T1), which also received massage

treatment, Sasso hen teaser (T2), and local hen teaser (T3). Another set of four Sasso hens and four local hens were kept apart and employed as teasers to rouse the Sasso cocks in T2 and T3, making it easier to collect semen without massage. During the ~~teaser interaction period~~, only to the cocks in T2 and T3 twice daily but were not allowed to mount. A total of twelve (12) Sasso cocks (24 weeks of age) were randomly selected from the Livestock Farm. The imported eggs of Sasso which originated from France, were brought in from Tanzania and hatched at Fol-Hope Farms Ltd, New Airport Road, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The day-old

chicks (DOC) arrived at the Livestock Farm on 11th August 2016. The cocks were reared intensively for two (2) weeks. All the Sasso cocks were raised under a deep litter system provided with a diet of breeder mash and water *ad libitum*.

Semen Collection Techniques

Massage technique

The ejaculatory papillae were made to enlarge by gently stroking the back feather with one hand while massaging the abdomen toward the tail with the other hand to activate the copulatory appendage. According to Burrows and Quinn (1937), a capillary tube was utilised in the semen collection process after the enlarged ejaculatory papillae eventually secreted semen.

Use of teaser technique

One by one, the Sasso cocks were brought to a teaser hen respectively. At the moment of ejaculation, the cock was lifted after being allowed to mount the teaser for a brief period. Semen was secreted on the enlarged ejaculatory papillae without any massage and a capillary tube was employed for the collection, as outlined by Burrows and Quinn (1937).

Data collection and statistical analysis

The cocks' semen was extracted using a massage technique on the abdomen. The ejaculate's spermatozoa concentration, motility, colour, volume, and pH were all estimated. The cocks' semen was extracted using a massage technique on the abdomen. The ejaculate's spermatozoa concentration, motility, colour, volume, and pH were all estimated. The spermatozoa content, motility, color, volume, and pH of the ejaculate were all estimated. A pipette that had been calibrated was used to measure the volume of ejaculate. Using a microscope, sperm motility was subjectively evaluated. Peters *et al.* (2008) explain that by utilizing a calibrated pH meter to measure the ejaculate's pH, we were able to visually differentiate the three different ejaculate colors: creamy white, opaque and creamy- white, and opaque. Three minutes after the values were collected and they were recorded. Each cock's semen colour was determined by visual inspection. The spermatozoa concentration was estimated using the hemocytometric method. To evaluate the morphological changes of ejaculates, a 1:5 dilution ratio of 0.5% saline solution was used. This was done following the method of evaluating the number of degenerated spermatozoa, the head, the midpiece, and the tail (frequencies were expressed in percents), as well as the occurrence of developmental anomalies (Hermiz *et al.*, 2016; Sun *et al.*, 2019). The midpiece adjustments were described as narrowing, widening, and/or distorting; the head changes were described as being too big or too little, twisted, curled, or missing; and the tail changes were described as twisting, bending, and/or not present. All spermatozoa with developmental defects were classified as degenerated. Data collected were analyzed using one- way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using the SPSS statistical software version 2010. Means were separated using the least

significant difference (LSD) method at a 5% probability level.

3. RESULTS

The impact of teaser hens on the quantity, quality, and spermatozoa traits of Sasso cocks is displayed in Table 1. All the parameters measured showed no statistical differences ($P < 0.05$), except for semen volume, total semen count and response

time to semen collection. Cocks that were confronted with another cock as a teaser in their cage showed tremendous exaltation and responded right away, but they did not generate any semen. The male may need more stimulation than the 60s and occasionally tends to fight with the inserted cock as a teaser. When the hen is used as a teaser, the Sasso cock quickly responded by climbing onto the hen's back and making an attempt at copulation in response to the hen's presence and extreme exaltation.

Table 1: Impact of Teaser Hens on the Semen Production, Quality, and Spermatozoa Features of Sasso Cocks

Parameter	T1	T2	
T3 Number of Cocks	4	4	4
Bodyweight (kg)	3.82±0.58	3.77±0.56	4.19±0.18
Live sperm (%)	54.00±13.64	63.75±14.63	59.75±18.08
Active sperm cell motile (%)	62.00±14.88	64.25±13.68	68.75±12.48
Sluggish motile sperm cell (%)	13.00±4.06	35.75±13.68	30.25±13.20
Dead sperm cell (%)	46.00±13.64	33.75±12.81	40.25±18.08
PH concentration	7.80±0.49	7.25±0.48	7.13±0.13
Glucose concentration (mol/l)	7.20±1.70	5.50±0.00	5.38±0.13
Total count (×10cells/l)	165.48±13.7	558.40±96.62?	590.40±119.67?

^{ab} = Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability.

* = Significant at a 5% level of probability.

NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

T= Treatment

T1 (Control): Massage technique; T2: Use of Sasso hen as a teaser; T3: Use of local hen as a teaser.

LOS = Level of significance.

DISCUSSION According to (Obidi *et al.*, 2008), cockerels are seasonal breeders and typically generate more semen at the beginning of the breeding season (long day length) and reduced volumes towards the conclusion. Light intensity also influences semen characteristics in both the warm and cold seasons, leading to lower ejaculate volumes compared to the rainy season, which might be due to decreased spermatogenesis and an increased sperm mortality rate. Additionally, a brief reduction in spermatozoa production due to high relative humidity results in reduced ejaculate volumes and sperm concentrations, which may have an impact on spermatozoa mortality and fertility (Obidi *et al.*, 2008). For several chicken breeds, the average ejaculate volume of a cockerel has been calculated to be 0.7 millilitres (Tuncer *et al.*, 2008). Breed, age, body weight, excessive stimulation, season, and environmental factors, especially cock management, may have contributed to the decreased semen volumes. All breed/strain ejaculate volumes recorded in this study were smaller than this 0.7±0.12 ml. The ejaculate quantities found in this study fall within the permissible range for artificial insemination of poultry and are comparable to those found by other researchers (Hafez & Hafez, 2000). The mean ejaculate volume measured by other studies was 0.28±0.14 ml, which is less than what was found in this study (Tuncer *et al.*, 2008). The average ejaculate volume measured in this study fell between 0.34 and 0.59 millilitres, as reported by Lukaszewicz *et al.*, 2008; Mugiyono *et al.*, 2015). on broiler cocks, and between 0.40 and 0.73 millilitres, as reported by Peters *et al.*, (2008) on seven distinct native

Nigerian chickens. The PH of the semen varied significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) between the Sasso cocks. Semen PH varied significantly among the three treatments, averaging 7.80±0.49 for T1, 7.25±0.48 for T2, and 7.13±0.13 for T3 Sasso cock strains.

According to several studies (Bah *et al.*, 2001; Peters *et al.*, 2008; Tuncer *et al.*, 2008), the PH of cockerel semen was 7.02±0.01, 7.4±0.2, and 7.68±0.01. The method used to collect semen and stimulation of the accessory sex glands are two factors that may contribute to semen PH. According to Bah *et al.* (2001), the fluid from the auxiliary sex glands is often alkaline. Comparing crossbred cockerels to their purebred native counterparts, the active spermatozoa cell mortality was significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$). High spermatozoa mortality is thought to be a good indicator of high semen quality with acceptable fertilizing ability and good fertility (Azubuikwe *et al.*, 2017; Mavi *et al.*, 2019). Bah *et al.* (2001) observed spermatozoa mortality in fresh semen samples of males from New Hampshire that was 73.9±0.2% and 83.2±0.6% in white Leghorn, which is consistent with the findings of this study. Additionally, Peters *et al.* (2008) showed that enhanced indigenous crossbred (Alpha) cocks had a spermatozoa mortality rate of 82.50±10.00%.

In contrast, Mosene (2009) found that the spermatozoa mortality rates in Rhode Island Red, Potchefstroom Koekoek, New Hampshire, and white Leghorn, were, respectively, 59.6±14.3, 61.6±14.1%, 58.8±12.5%, and 63.8±13.6%. The season of semen collection may have contributed to the differences in spermatozoa mortality between the two investigations. While Monsene's (2009) investigation was conducted in the winter, the current study was conducted in the summer. It has been demonstrated that a high rate of spermatogenesis is favoured by the season.

High ejaculate volume, sperm concentration, and poultry fertility have also been linked to the wet season (Madubuike and Ekenyem (2005). Obidi *et al.* (2008) found that because cockerels breed seasonally, they frequently produce more semen at the start of the mating season (extended day length) and less at the conclusion. High relative humidity also temporarily lowers spermatozoa production, which leads to lower ejaculation volumes and spermatozoa concentrations, which may affect spermatozoa mortality and fertility (Obidi *et al.*, 2008). In this particular experiment, the ejaculate concentration of semen in treatment III is significantly higher than that of treatment I ($p \leq 0.05$). The spermatozoa cell concentration density frequently indicates the number of spermatozoa cells per unit volume (ml) of seminal plasma (Peters *et al.* 2008; Murugesan *et al.*, 2013; Adeoye *et al.*, 2018). Spermatozoa concentrations in both native and crossbred cocks were over 1.2 billion/ml and below 7.0 billion sperm/ml semen (Hafez & Hafez, 2000). The strains' disparate genetic backgrounds are the only explanation for the discrepancies in sperm concentration. Because greater heterozygosity of heterosis has a positive influence on fitness traits (survival and reproduction), crossbred cocks may have higher concentrations of spermatozoa than their native counterparts. Peters *et al.* (2008) found strain-specific variations in semen concentration in native Nigerian cocks, which is in line with this. The three treatments had a substantial impact on the viability of spermatozoa (dead and living sperm) in the Sasso cocks that were the subject of the study. The study found a high percentage of live spermatozoa, with an average of I - 63.75 ± 14.63 for live spermatozoa and II = 64.25 ± 13.68 for active spermatozoa cells.

According to findings from Tunsisa and Berihun, 2022), the proportion of live spermatozoa in cockerel semen that are without abnormalities ranges from 58% to 80%. This is also consistent with the results of this study. The number of live spermatozoa was recorded as 54.00 ± 13.64 , 63.75 ± 14.63 , and 59.75 ± 18.08 , as per Monsene *et al.*, (2009). During the process of semen collection, the percentage of dead spermatozoa in the three treatment Sasso cocks fluctuates between 46.00 ± 13.64 and $40.25 \pm 18.08\%$. Among the three treatments of the Sasso cock, the overall spermatozoa count ranged from 165. 48 ± 13.78^a to 558.40 ± 96^b to 590.40 ± 119.67 , showing a highly significant difference at ($p \leq 0.05$).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Sasso cocks are thought to produce higher-quality semen than their purebred counterparts. Therefore, with the right care, Sasso cocks can be employed as a tactic to raise the quality of native hens' semen. Teasers in semen collection could be an alternate way in poultry since the Sasso cocks responded favourably to the use of teaser hens in semen collection and the spermatozoa and semen quality attributes appeared to be unaffected by it.

Sasso birds should be made available to farmers to boost output, achieve good breeding, and improve poultry industry performance to improve Nigerians' nutritional intake. Although Sasso cocks seemed to respond to teaser hens in semen gathering, the qualities of the spermatozoa and the quality of the semen seemed to be unaffected. In poultry species, teasers may be used to collect semen, as is already the case with some animals. To improve poultry productivity and further avian research, however, more thorough research on the use of different teasers would be required.

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